

A1313

Process optimization of a SOFC system for the combined production of hydrogen and electricity

M. Pérez-Fortes (1), A. Mian (1), S. Diethelm (1), L. Wang (1), F. Maréchal (1), J. Van herle (1), S. Santhanam (2), M.P. Heddrich (2), S.F. Au (3), E. Varkaraki (3), Z. Wuillemin (3), R. Makkus (4), I. Mirabelli (4), R. Schoon (5), M. Grippa (6) M. Testi (7), L. Crema (7)

(1) École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, 1951 Sion, Switzerland

(2) German Aerospace Center, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany

(3) SOLIDpower / HTceramix SA, 1400 Yverdon-les-Bain, Switzerland

(4) HyGear B. V., 6802 EG Arnhem, The Netherlands

(5) Shell Global Solutions International B.V., 1031 HW Amsterdam, The Netherlands

(6) Vertech Group, 11 Rue Defly 06000 Nice, France

(7) Fondazione Bruno Kessler, 38050 Povo (Trento), Italy

Tel.: +41-21-69-35968

mar.perezfortes@epfl.ch

Abstract

The objective of the CH2P project is the cogeneration of hydrogen (H₂), heat and power using a solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) system fueled by a methane rich gas. The CH2P plant consists of natural gas sulfur removal, fuel pre-reforming, steam generation, SOFC stacks, H₂ separation (through a combination of water-gas shift – WGS reactors and pressure swing adsorption – PSA) and the heat exchanger network (HEN). The plant will be the main production technology for a hydrogen refueling station (HRS), providing the daily demand of H₂ and producing electricity for both self-consumption and other uses, for example, for grid balancing and fast charging of electric vehicles. Different usage scenarios are defined for the cogeneration of H₂ and power in the CH2P plant. It is therefore crucial to know the characteristics of each period: H₂ demand, electricity needed and generated, minimum and maximum loads and temperature conditions. An appropriate design of the HEN has to satisfy the different operating periods.

In order to optimize the CH2P plant operating conditions and provide the best HEN configuration capable to fulfill the requested outputs for all periods, the proposed methodology follows a systematic approach for multi-objective and multi-period optimization. The solving strategy combines process flow modelling, pinch analysis and superstructure based mathematical modelling. The methodology is applied to the CH2P project to generate solutions at maximum efficiency and minimum number of heat exchanger matches. The results show that the plant can reach a daily weighted efficiency exceeding 60 %.

Introduction

The transition towards a renewable and more efficient transport sector requires the installation of refueling stations of the next generation. The market penetration of fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEV) goes along with the development of an appropriate H₂ distribution infrastructure. Hydrogen refueling station (HRS) networks are being deployed in Japan, California and Germany, where H₂ is often delivered in pressurized tanks and derives from fossil fuels. Alternatively, H₂ can be produced on-site by electrolysis using renewable electricity and stored until further consumption [1].

The EU H2020 CH2P project (*Fostering the clean transport transition for a healthy place to live!*) proposes a novel and transitional HRS concept based on the on-site H₂ production by methane reforming, which takes place in a pre-reformer and inside a solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC). The HRS produces as well (i) the electricity that is required by the retail station (convenience shop, car wash, selling of conventional fuels) and the HRS itself, and/or that can be injected into the grid or supplied to battery electric vehicles (BEV), and (ii) heat that can be used elsewhere. The priorities of the CH2P plant in terms of electricity and H₂ productions to be fulfilled are summarized in Table 1. These periods include variations of power demand and H₂ production, and are based on operating HRS experience.

Table 1. Periods of the CH2P plant. Full capacity of electricity production is 25 kW, and full capacity of H₂ production is 20 kg/day.

Periods	Electricity generation (required or % of full capacity)	Hydrogen generation (% of full capacity)
1	Retail station	10 %
2	Retail station + HRS	100 %
3	100 %	100 %
4	50 %	50 %
5	100 %	0 %

A challenge is the identification of a single heat exchanger network (HEN) that is able to operate at all the specified periods. A multi-period HEN, as defined in the current work, provides the heating and cooling requirements for the different periods, with the same set of heat exchangers (HEX). The knowledge of the system's operation characteristics for each period is central to (i) propose the optimum matches between hot and cold process streams and the available utilities, and (ii) determine the optimal operation temperatures of each HEX. The present work uses and adapts the systematic and combinatorial approach for multi-period optimization developed by A. Mian and co-workers [2,3], which combines pinch analysis and mathematical modelling. The novelty of the current work lies in the application of a multi-objective and multi-period optimization approach for the conceptual design of a SOFC-based HRS.

1. Approach

The proposed methodology follows the systematic approach developed since long of the tool OSMOSE at the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) [4]. OSMOSE is a computer platform that bridges models and data flows from different software and tools to aid (systematic) decision-making. Figure 1 summarizes the main steps of the multi-objective optimization (MOO) methodology developed for the purpose of the current work. ASPEN PLUS software is used for the CH2P process flow modelling in steady state (as shown in Figure 2). The SYNHEAT superstructure stands for the type of HEX connections and layout

(i.e. parallel and series HEX, definition of a number of temperature stages, consideration of stream bypass, split and isothermal mixture) which was originally proposed in [5]. The SYNHEAT algorithm from [3], which integrates the utility streams among the HEN (not only at the extremes), is modified to take into account the multi-period optimization strategy from [2]. The core of the MOO methodology is an evolutionary algorithm developed at EPFL for energy system optimizations. It is a steady state algorithm, elitist to improve convergence and it uses clustering to preserve the diversity of the candidate population [6]. It forms the master or upper optimization level of the iterative solution process, with the subsequent steps executed by MATLAB routines (for data pre- and post-processing –including calculation of objective functions, filtering and communication among software’s) as the slave or lower optimization level. MOO algorithm is indeed used to identify the most appropriate input values of the defined decision variables, by manipulations driven by the results of the objective functions. The developed workflow comprises calls to the mathematical programming language AMPL and the mixed integer linear program (MILP) solver CPLEX. Pinch point process integration techniques are used to solve the heat cascade and maximize heat recovery.

Figure 1. Sequential multi-objective optimization (MOO) workflow applied in the multi-period optimization of the CH2P plant.

The change of the decision variables drives a new ASPEN PLUS calculation, the results of which are evaluated in the SYNHEAT algorithm: network inlet and outlet temperatures, heat load and heat transfer coefficients of every cold and hot stream, to obtain a HEN proposal (configuration and scheduling) and a weighted efficiency value.

The following capabilities and hypotheses are considered in the developed approach:

- The possibility of including forbidden and restricted matches among streams, as well as of the declaration of non-splittable streams, is implemented (see Section 2 for further detail).
- Heat transfer coefficients are assumed constant for all the periods. Planar counter-flow exchangers are considered.
- The dynamics when changing flowrates or temperatures between periods, e.g. residence times and thermal inertia, are neglected.

The calculation of the overall heat transfer coefficients (U , $W/m^2\text{°C}$) accounts for the film transfer coefficient of each individual cold or hot stream (h , $W/m^2\text{°C}$) evaluated at mean properties values. Film transfer coefficients are evaluated following the expressions and hypotheses from [7–10]. The overall heat transfer coefficients are evaluated taking into account a temperature correction factor [8] and an area increase due to fouling [10]. The wall resistance is considered negligible [7].

The optimization problem formulation comprises objective functions, independent (or decision) variables and constraints. The independent variables are changed (within a specified range of values) by the evolutionary algorithm for the screening of solutions. In an evolutionary algorithm, the constraints (or conditions that must be fulfilled) are not enforced, but verified by filtering. The solution procedure follows three steps: (i) optimization of each period individually, (ii) bi-period optimization (considering the two most relevant periods for CH₂P operation) and (iii) multi-period optimization (considering the 5 periods proposed).

2. Problem Statement and Calculations

The CH₂P plant, as depicted in Figure 2, consists of a natural gas sulfur removal step and a natural gas mixture with steam followed by methane pre-reforming. In parallel, water is converted into steam before being mixed with natural gas. The H₂-rich stream enters the SOFC stack, together with air. The cathode off-gas is sent to the burner, or further cooled down before venting. The anode off-gas proceeds to the H₂ separation section, via two-stage water-gas shift (WGS) reactor and pressure swing adsorption – PSA. The H₂ stream is further compressed up to 30 bar. Important considerations for the MOO resolution are:

- Q13 and the reformer (C102) are physically the same unit, and thus must be heated up by the same stream.
- The water knock-out process occurs at 35 °C. Thus, T_{out} of Q8 is 35 °C.
- T_{out} of Q5 and Q9 are fixed at 160 °C (i.e. temperature of vented gases).
- T_{out} of Q6 (high temperature – HT- WGS) is 325 °C and of Q7 (low temperature – LT- WGS) is 200 °C.
- There are 5 hot streams: Q5, Q6, Q7, Q8 and Q9,
- and 7 cold streams: Q1, Q4, Q13, Q2SH, Q2E, Q2EV, C102 (Q2-SH, -E and -EV stand for super-heater, economizer and evaporator).
- 4 temperature stages (as defined by the SYNHEAT algorithm).
- Q2EV and C102 are streams at constant temperature.
- One cold utility: water that can be used in the retail station as hot water (with a temperature range from 20 to 65 °C).
- Forbidden matches: Q6-Q1, Q7-Q1, Q8-Q1, Q9-Q13, Q9-C102, to avoid contact between a combustible gas and oxygen.
- No splitting of high temperature streams (above 500 °C), so no parallel heat exchange is allowed in the streams: Q5, Q6, Q9, Q4 and C102, so as to avoid the use of high temperature valves.
- Constant heat losses in SOFC stack, reformer, burner, WGS reactors and Q1.
- The cold utility circuit for the cooling of the compression stages is not modelled.
- ΔT_{min} of 50 °C for the hot and cold streams exchange, ΔT_{min} of 100 °C for the hot and cold streams exchange at temperatures above 500 °C (Q4, C102, Q5, Q6, Q9) and ΔT_{min} of 5 °C for the hot stream-cold utility exchange.
- For the calculation of a weighted efficiency, the time of operation of periods 2 and 3 is 9 h/day for each one of them; of periods 1, 4 and 5 it is 2 h/day. For bi-period optimization, it is assumed that periods 2 and 3 operate each for 12 h/day.

Figure 2. Process flow diagram (PFD) that summarizes the layout characteristics and the cold and hot streams that have to be considered for optimization. Two process layouts are taken into account (represented by a two-fold discontinuous line in the PFD): (i) without cathode off-gas combustion (option A) and (ii) with cathode off-gas sent to the burner (option B).

Objective functions

1. Maximization of the efficiency. The weighted efficiency encompasses all the single period efficiencies, as in Eq.(1), and an average number of hours per day, as described before. Hydrogen and electricity productions are considered in terms of power. Net electricity is calculated from the SOFC gross power, in view of own electricity needs, with H₂ conditioning compression up to 30 bar.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\dot{m}_{H_2} * LHV_{H_2} + Net\ electricity}{\dot{m}_{NG} * LHV_{NG}} \quad (1)$$

where m are mass flowrates in kg/s, NG stands for natural gas and LHV for the lower heating values in kJ/kg (120 210 kJ/kg for H₂ and 38 050 kJ/kg for Dutch natural gas). Net electricity is expressed in kW.

2. Minimization of the number of heat exchanger matches. This is a discrete objective. As such, only integer numbers can be considered, and the range of variability is small, as the same heat-cooling needs have to be fulfilled.

Independent variables

1. Binary variable. Two process layouts are considered: (i) without cathode off-gas combustion (option A) and (ii) with cathode off-gas sent to the burner (option B). This consideration results into two sets of optimization results.
2. Continuous variables. See Table 2.

Constraints

Table 3 gathers the numerical constraints used in the optimization procedure.

Table 2. Continuous decision variables used in the multi-objective optimization.*The amount needed (without restrictions) to provide the required power and heat load, at each period.

Independent variables	Range
1. Fuel inlet temperature SOFC (outlet temperature of Q4)	680-740 °C
2. Air inlet temperature SOFC (outlet temperature of Q1)	690-750 °C
3. Air flowrate in the SOFC	0.028-0.13 kg/s
4. Q13 outlet temperature (T pre-reforming)	350-670 °C
5. Fuel utilization (FU)	0.20-0.85
6. T out burner (inlet temperature for Q5)	825-950 °C
7. Natural gas fed into the SOFC	kg/s*
8. Natural gas fed into the burner	kg/s*

Table 3. Constraints used in the multi-objective optimization (solutions filtering).

Constraints	Value
1. CO molar fraction at the inlet of the PSA	< 0.01
2. Oxygen utilization in the SOFC	0-0.33
3. λ in the SOFC	≥ 2.5
4. Q13 outlet temperature	$\leq T_{Q4}$
5. T out SOFC	≤ 800 °C
6. Cell voltage (V_{cell})	> 0.7 V

The SOFC current density, air ratio λ in the burner and temperature of reforming (T of Q13), were extracted for each iteration (and eventually used for the control of the optimization process). The ΔT in the fuel cell was calculated and monitored as well (looking for the minimum value).

Solution procedure

The optimization problem has 8 decision variables (Table 2) and applies 6 filters (Table 3). The first attempt considered the complete set of 8 decision variables, for the 5 periods of operation at the same time, since the SYNHEAT algorithm needs the information of all the periods for the HEN design, yielding a 40 variables problem. The solution procedure was divided in three main steps, to decrease the number of variables, and thus, to decrease computational time.

- Optimization of each period individually, considering the overall 8 variables per iteration (performing up to 10 000 iterations per period). The best performing variable's values are selected for each one of the periods by filtering the highest efficiencies. Constraints, such as gross power and H₂ needs are monitored.
- Bi-period optimization. The HEN proposed in the bi-period optimization only considers periods 2 and 3, which are the most relevant for the CH₂P plant. Seven out of 8 variables are fixed according to the best performing cases of the previous step. Only one variable is optimized in the current run: the flowrate of natural gas going into the burner (variable 8). Therefore, a total of 1 variable x 2 period's variables are considered in each iteration. Once a natural gas flow is determined, the multi-period SYNHEAT algorithm calculates the amount of cooling water and the minimum number of stream connections to satisfy the heat-cooling needs. Analogously to the previous case, the best performing variable's values are selected for each one of the periods by filtering the highest efficiencies. Constraints, gross power and H₂ needs are monitored as well.
- Multi-period optimization. In this case, the proposed HEN meets all period's requirements. The followed approach is the same as that in the bi-period optimization, and thus, 1x5 variables are considered in each iteration.

The optimization procedure results in a HEN, based on a common set of connections for the 5 periods, together with the corresponding set of operating conditions, according to Table 2. The optimization result does not provide with common exchanger's areas, to maintain the linearity of the mathematical problem. In the following step after optimization, the practical target goes towards the heuristic minimization of the number of bypasses and parallel exchangers, to propose a common HEN with common UA factors for all the periods. The use of UA factors, which stands for the overall heat transfer coefficient multiplied by the exchange area, instead of areas of exchange, aims at mitigating the uncertainty related to the estimation of heat transfer coefficients and thus, alleviating imprecision when using the calculated data for pilot plant HEN design.

3. Results and Discussion

The composite curves of the CH₂P process, before heat integration and with a unique ΔT_{\min} value for all the streams, are shown in Figure 3, for period 3 and option B (cathode off-gas sent to the burner), as an example. They show that the case study is in essence a threshold problem requiring only a cold utility, as the hot needs are provided by the natural gas sent to the burner inside the plant layout. The cold composite curve shows the two isothermal processes: reforming and evaporation. The hot composite curve is characterized by the high temperature of the flue gas, which is the main stream that provides heat to all the system. The cold utility is needed at low temperature, more specifically, for water condensation.

Figure 3. General composite curves for period 3 and option B, with an overall ΔT_{\min} of 15 °C.

Common set of connections

The HEN obtained following the described methodology is depicted in Figure 4 and Figure 5, for options A or B (regarding cathode off-gas possibilities), and for a common set of HEX connections. The resulting HEN for option A has 13 HEX, while that for option B has 12 HEX. The HEN connections, and proposed HEX sizes, can be considered a theoretical optimum: the solution has to be simplified and revised, for real implementation. Note that connections (bypass-mixer) that are only active for one/some of the operation periods, are depicted with dashed lines.

Table 4 and Table 5 summarize the variables values (from 1 to 7, Table 2) obtained in the optimization of each period individually, for each flowsheet configuration. The reported value for variable 8 corresponds to the multi-period optimization.

Figure 4. HEN proposed for option A based on multi-period optimization.

Figure 5. HEN proposed for option B based on multi-period optimization.

Table 6 points out that a common HEN induces higher use of natural gas as hot utility, exchanging heat at the hottest stage, triggering lower efficiency values. The option which counts with cathode off-gas sent to the burner, option B, provides a higher efficiency, above 66.5 %, for period 3 and overall, provides a larger weighted efficiency. Note that the

weighted efficiency can be penalised by the low efficiency of periods that are less used, resulting in larger values for the bi-period optimizations.

Table 4. Variable values obtained in the multi-objective optimization for flowsheet option A and multi-period resolution.

Variables	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4	Period 5
1. T _{in} fuel SOFC (°C)	734	736	705	686	682
2. T _{in} air SOFC (°C)	719	699	696	690	690
3. Air flowrate in SOFC (kg/s)	0.028	0.056	0.061	0.036	0.089
4. T _{out} Q13 (°C)	470	456	468	525	489
5. FU	0.504	0.224	0.482	0.466	0.841
6. T _{out} burner (°C)	912	930	908	943	903
7. Natural gas fed into the SOFC (kg/s)	2.88e ⁻⁴	1.51e ⁻³	1.86e ⁻³	8.99e ⁻⁴	1.12e ⁻³
8. Natural gas fed into the burner (kg/s)	4.54e ⁻⁴	3.05e ⁻⁴	3.77e ⁻⁴	5.21e ⁻⁴	7e ⁻⁴

Table 5. Variable values obtained in the multi-objective optimization for flowsheet option B and multi-period resolution.

Variables	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4	Period 5
1. T _{in} fuel SOFC (°C)	713	722	691	693	718
2. T _{in} air SOFC (°C)	733	704	694	704	708
3. Air flowrate in SOFC (kg/s)	0.030	0.059	0.064	0.032	0.088
4. T _{out} Q13 (°C)	601	533	445	487	459
5. FU	0.508	0.225	0.481	0.471	0.828
6. T _{out} burner (°C)	904	946	894	912	833
7. Natural gas fed into the SOFC (kg/s)	2.80e ⁻⁴	1.53e ⁻³	1.90e ⁻³	8e ⁻⁴	1.11e ⁻³
8. Natural gas fed into the burner (kg/s)	2.67e ⁻⁴	3.42e ⁻⁵	1.53e ⁻⁴	4.20e ⁻⁴	4.37e ⁻⁴

Based on the obtained results, the next step is to propose a HEN that can operate during the 5 periods with common UA factors.

Table 6. Efficiency values (%) obtained for both flowsheet options.

		Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4	Period 5	Weighted
Option A	Individual	31.7	49.8	60.1	50.3	55.8	52.7
	Bi-period		48.9	60.1			54.5
	Multi-period	29.2	48.8	60.1	46.6	45.1	50.9
Option B	Individual	45.9	60.3	67.4	61.6	58.4	61.7
	Bi-period		60.3	67.4			63.9
	Multi-period	39.6	60.1	66.5	48.7	54.1	59.3

Common heat exchange UA factors

The selected multi-period option B is further adapted with stream's splitters and mixers to conveniently accommodate the different heating/cooling needs. The considered design conditions to be met are summarized in Table 7, as optimization is not performed in this step. Note that the manual adaptation of the proposed HEN connections requires the relaxation of some temperature values that were considered as fixed during the optimization step. These values are listed in Table 7 as constraints and correspond to the inlet temperatures of the PSA, water treatment plant, WGS reactors, and the outlet temperatures of flue gases and superheated steam (constraints 11 to 16). The manual adaptation of the proposed HEN connections requires as well the conversion of some independent variables (Table 2) into dependent variables; these are the SOFC inlet fuel and air temperatures and the temperature of pre-reforming. Overall, the practical target goes towards the heuristic minimization of the number of bypasses and parallel heat exchangers.

The steps following the determination of a common set of HEN connections and driven to find a common set of HEX for all 5 periods, are:

- The selection of the largest UA factors per heat exchanger among the results obtained for each period after multi-period optimization,
- the elimination of the heat exchangers that are bypassed in any of the periods,
- the change of intermediate temperatures (stage temperatures), while keeping set point temperatures, and the adjustment of the variables $T_{out\ burner}$ (and the consequent stream of air going to the burner), i.e. independent variable number 6 (in Table 2), and natural gas stream that goes to the burner, i.e. independent variable number 8 (in Table 2).

Table 7. Constraints used in the design of the HEN.

Constraints	Range
1. Fuel inlet temperature SOFC	680-780 °C
2. Air inlet temperature SOFC	680-780 °C
3. Air flowrate in the SOFC	0.028-0.13 kg/s
4. Temperature of reforming	≥ 350 °C
5. $T_{out\ burner}$	825-950 °C
6. $T_{out\ SOFC}$	≤ 800 °C
7. Oxygen utilization in the SOFC	0-0.33
8. λ in the SOFC	≥ 2.5
9. Cell voltage (V_{cell})	> 0.7 V
10. CO molar fraction at the inlet of the PSA	< 0.01
11. T before PSA	25-35 °C
12. T before water treatment plant	35-40 °C
13. $T_{out\ flue\ gases}$	< 160 °C
14. T in high temperature WGS	About 325 °C
15. T in low temperature WGS	About 200 °C
16. T of superheated steam	free

The operating conditions for each period are listed in Table 8. Figure 6 shows a solution with 8 HEX. In this case, period 1 is the less favorable, because the HEN identified to simultaneously fulfill all the requirements is actually over-dimensioned for the electricity and H_2 requirements of period 1. Period 1 needs an “extra” splitting-mixing combination in the flue gas stream. Periods 1, 2 and 4 use a splitting-mixing combination of the H_2 -rich anode off-gas to control WGS reactors temperatures. Note that the efficiencies in Table 8 are higher than the efficiencies reported in Table 6 (for option B and multi-period optimization) mainly due to the relaxation of different temperature values that were considered fixed before, and due to the layout changes.

Table 8. Variable values and efficiencies obtained for flowsheet option B with a common HEN for all the periods. Weighted efficiency: 62.8 %

Variables	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4	Period 5
1. $T_{in\ fuel\ SOFC}$ (°C)	757	722	685	754	769
2. $T_{in\ air\ SOFC}$ (°C)	717	736	709	729	706
3. Air flowrate in SOFC (kg/s)	0.030	0.059	0.064	0.032	0.088
4. $T_{out\ Q13}$ (°C)	350	547	517	695	663
5. FU	0.508	0.225	0.481	0.471	0.828
6. $T_{out\ burner}$ (°C)	825	950	937	912	850
7. Natural gas fed into the SOFC (kg/s)	2.80e ⁻⁴	1.53e ⁻³	1.90e ⁻³	8e ⁻⁴	1.11e ⁻³
8. Natural gas fed into the burner (kg/s)	1.30e ⁻⁴	2.06e ⁻⁵	1.30e ⁻⁴	1.10e ⁻⁴	3.03e ⁻⁴
Efficiency (%)	53.4	61.3	67.0	67.0	55.6

Figure 6. HEN proposed for option B, with common UA factors and further relaxation of constraints.

4. Conclusions and Outlook

A methodology for the calculation of a heat exchanger network (HEN) has been implemented within the framework of the EU H2020 CH2P project. The novelty of the current work lies in the application of a multi-objective and multi-period optimization approach for the conceptual design of a SOFC-based HRS. It required extending the capability of the software tools available at the start of the project to include in the workflow methods recently developed for multi-period optimization [2,3]. The interface functionalities required specifically for the CH2P project were coded in a separated and dedicated standalone set of MATLAB routines. The present study is an illustration of the capability of the developed tool that can be adapted and used for the HEN conceptual design of other systems, for which the principles of the SYNHEAT algorithm are relevant. The sequence in the identification of viable solutions started with HEN topologies proposed by MOO. Several layout and unit's assessments were then made to achieve a single set of HEX, including practical considerations that cannot be implemented in a MILP model for MOO. An example of an outcome for the CH2P plant is a configuration comprising 8 planar HEX (characterized by their UA factor), yielding period efficiencies (considering H₂ compression up to 30 bar) that range from 53 % (period 1) to 67 % (periods 3 and 4). The cold utility considered is cooling water heated up to 65 °C, which can be used in the HRS as a cogeneration option.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 735692. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the

European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, from Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research. Swiss partners receive funding from the State Secretariat of Education, Research and Innovation (SEFRI), contract 16.0223.

Thanks to Steve Joris from EPFL for HEN drawing, Priscilla Caliandro and Arata Nakajo from EPFL for their advice and fruitful discussions.

References

- [1] H2ME Consortium, Hydrogen Mobility Europe, (2018). <http://h2me.eu/> (accessed May 7, 2018).
- [2] A. Mian, E. Martelli, F. Maréchal, Framework for the multiperiod sequential synthesis of heat exchanger networks with selection, design, and scheduling of multiple utilities, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 55 (2016) 168–186.
- [3] E. Martelli, C. Elsidio, A. Mian, F. Maréchal, MINLP model of two-stage algorithm for the simultaneous synthesis of heat exchanger networks, utility systems and heat recovery cycles, *Comput. Chem. Eng.* (2017) 1–27. doi:10.1016/j.compchemeng.2017.01.043.
- [4] Industrial Process and Energy Systems Engineering Group, IPESE group from EPFL website, (2018). <https://ipese.epfl.ch/ipese/software> (accessed May 8, 2018).
- [5] T.. Yee, I.E. Grossmann, Simultaneous optimization models for heat integration - II. Heat exchanger network synthesis, *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 14 (1990) 1165–1184.
- [6] A. Molyneaux, G. Leyland, D. Favrat, Environomic multi-objective optimisation of a district heating network considering centralized and decentralized heat pumps, *Energy.* 35 (2010) 751–758. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2009.09.028.
- [7] J. Kerner, Compact, high-efficiency heat exchangers: Understanding fouling, *Chem. Eng.* 118 (2011) 35–43.
- [8] G. Towler, R. Sinnott, *Chemical engineering design: principles, practice and economics of plant and process design*, 2nd ed., Butterworth-Heinemann, Elsevier, 2013.
- [9] R. Smith, *Chemical Process Design and Integration*, John Wiley & Sons Ltd, 2005.
- [10] D.W. Green, R.H. Perry, *Perry's Chemical Engineers' Handbook - Heat transfer equipment section*, McGraw-Hill, 1999.